

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 61(2) (2025) 124-142

EISSN 2543-5426

Comparative study of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* bioethanol production from cassava, yam, and rice husks

Ibiam Prince Amauche*, Okafor Blessing Onyinye, Titus Chinedu Egbosiuba, Maduegbunam Hope Ukamaka

Department of Chemical Engineering, College of Engineering,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Uli, Anambra State, Nigeria

*E-mail address: p.ibiam@gregoryuniversiutyuturu.edu.ng , ibiamprince72@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Bioethanol is a sustainable alcohol-based fuel derived from a range of biological sources. It is mostly made by fermenting the sugars found in crops including corn, sugarcane, wheat, and other agricultural goods. As part of the process, these carbohydrates are converted into ethanol by bacteria or yeast. Bioethanol is widely used as a biofuel component in petrol with the aim of reducing greenhouse gas emissions and dependency on fossil fuels. It is seen as a more environmentally friendly option because it produces fewer emissions when burned than regular fuel. Also, it can be combined with petrol in different proportions (such as E10 or E30), and cars that run on flexible fuels are designed to use these blends interchangeably. Around the world, there is widespread support for replacing fossil fuels with renewable energy sources. Our lives have depended on fossil fuels for energy, but we cannot ignore the dangers they provide; instead, we require an alternative energy source that is both environmentally benign and does not pose a threat to human life. This study emphasizes on producing bioethanol, an alternative fuel source, using rice husk, cassava peels, and yam peels. Rice husk, cassava, and yam peels were fermented at 48-, 72-, and 96-hour intervals to yield bioethanol with the aid of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Meyen ex E.C. Hansen. By distilling the fermenting liquid at 78 °C, the amount of bioethanol generated was determined. utilizing varying H_2SO_4 concentrations to hydrolyze yeast and agricultural waste. For different retention times and fermentation, the peak masses of 500g of rice husk, yam peel, and cassava peel were 3.19g, 5.58g, and 6.46g, respectively. This study shows that the peels of rice husks, cassava, and yams can be used to make bioethanol. Cassava peels produced the maximum yield because of their increased starch content, which was attained by employing more yeast.

Keywords: Comparative Study, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, Bioethanol, Cassava, Yam, Rice Husks

1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout the 20th century, the production of fuels, chemicals, materials, and electricity was mostly reliant on fossil fuels like coal, natural gas, and petroleum. Transportation and agriculture are the two main industries that use fossil fuels. But according to [1, 2], it exacerbates environmental damage and global warming. The negative environmental effects of fossil fuels over the past few decades, including increased global warming brought on by greenhouse gas emissions (such as CO, CO₂, CH₄, and NO₂), ongoing energy demand, dwindling energy supply sources, and the lack of a stable oil market, have made the search for alternative fuels necessary.

The sharp rise in GHG emissions also contributes to an increase in a number of illnesses. The transport industry is responsible for roughly 22% of global greenhouse gas emissions [3, 4]. It is anticipated that between 2020 and 2035, 8.6 billion metric tons of GHG emissions will be discharged into the atmosphere. Due to this increase in GHG emissions, the global temperature will rise by 2 °C, potentially killing hundreds of millions of people. Cosmetics, solvents, preservatives, and above all motor fuel (a petrol additive) are all applications for bioethanol [5].

Although the product is in great demand due to these essential applications, the food industries also employ the feedstock (cassava, yam, potatoes, sugar cane, and cereals) needed to make first-generation biofuels. An inevitable conflict between food production and bioethanol production has been brought to light by this duality. This thesis investigates the production of bioethanol from rice husk, yam, and cassava peelings as waste products in order to reduce the stem competitive demand of agricultural feedstock for bioethanol production, as this feedstock's used as food are not even adequate.

This thesis investigates the production of bioethanol from rice husk, yam, and cassava peelings as waste products in order to reduce the stem competitive demand for agricultural feedstock for bioethanol production, as this feedstock's used as food are insufficient for Africans to consume in a healthy manner. Simple sugar can be converted by microbes into ethanol and carbon (IV) oxide to produce bioethanol. In order to accomplish this, the following techniques are used: Enzyme hydrolysis, Acid hydrolysis, Fermentation and Distillation

When used in its purest form, bioethanol, a renewable energy source, might replace gasoline in moving automobiles. The fact that bioethanol lowers pollutant emissions by 80–90% is one of its environmental benefits [6, 7]. The Industrial Revolution has led to a rise in the demand for petroleum.

The necessity for an alternative fuel was prompted by the gas emissions from burning fossil fuels in recent decades. Diesel and petroleum are regarded as non-renewable fuels and will soon become limited. Carbon dioxide and other hazardous and volatile molecules that cause pollution and health risks, like benzene, toluene, and xylenes, are released in greater quantities when petroleum-based fuels are burned.

The development of alternative energy sources has been a major concern in recent years. The demand for ethanol increased as a result. The potential of bioethanol as an environmentally beneficial and renewable energy source was becoming widely acknowledged.

The reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, engine compression ratio, sustainability, and environmental pollution are only a few of the many advantages that biofuel generally offers [8].

Ten to fourteen percent of energy comes from biomass, which has been regarded as a substantial energy source.

Cellulose makes up a large portion of biomass that occurs naturally. The eventual significant source of bioethanol is anticipated to be cellulosic materials, which also serve as a technology that adds value to agricultural products. Bioethanol needs to be further purified before use, even though it is regarded as a renewable energy source. The ethanol industry most frequently uses rectification by additional distillation as a purifying method. Recent years have seen a significant increase in interest in bioethanol made from renewable biomass as a way to cut greenhouse gas emissions and the usage of fossil fuels [9].

Ethanol can be used as a transportation fuel and as an additive in gasoline to reduce pollution and global warming [10]. Rice husk, cassava starch, and sawdust are fermented to create this high octane number biofuel [11].

Over the past ten years, the majority of researchers have concentrated on creating an environmentally friendly and cost-effective ethanol production method. As the most plentiful and renewable resources on the planet, ethanol can be produced from agricultural and forestry leftovers as well as other types of biomass, which is why it is being prioritized [13].

First generation bioethanol is made by fermenting sugar-based raw materials, while second generation bioethanol is made by using lignocellulose-based raw materials [14]. Research on the third generation of algal bioethanol is still in its infancy. Additionally, cellulosic plants particularly agricultural food waste products like rice husk, bagasse, wheat straw, and rice straw represent an untapped source of fermentable sugars with substantial applications. Accordingly, lignocellulosic materials are used to produce second generation ethanol [15].

The cellulose and hemicellulose carbohydrates in these waste products are closely linked to the lignin found in plant cell walls. In order to release the carbohydrates for additional transformation steps, the lignin component must be eliminated because it functions as a physical barrier. Bioethanol production is made economical, environmentally benign, and renewable by utilizing microorganisms, particularly cellulose-degrading fungi, to bioconvert cellulosic biomass into fermentable sugar for ethanol production [16].

In order to manufacture biofuel, researchers are more interested in producing bioethanol from trash than energy crops, which compete with food crops for water and land. In order to address this conflict, it is vital to integrate all types of biowaste into the biomass economy. This is because rising food prices are discouraging the use of energy crops to make biofuel [17].

There has been a lot of interest in using lignocellulosic waste for the production and recovery of numerous value-added products because of its abundance and renewability, even though it is primarily wasted in the food processing industries' pre-harvest and post-harvest agricultural handling [18].

The pursuit and creation of alternative energy sources have attracted a lot of attention lately. This is demonstrated by the massive financial investments made by numerous governments and organizations worldwide to find a fuel source other than fossil fuels. Because fossil fuels are used to generate energy, the globe is facing major environmental risks such as ozone layer depletion and contamination of the air, land, and water.

An alternative fuel source that is less harmful to living systems, more economical, and environmentally benign is what this research attempts to provide [20].

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2. 1. Sample collection and processing of samples

2. 1. 1. Cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) peel

The cassava peels utilized in this study were gathered in May 2024 at the Gregory University Uturu Cassava Processing Factory. Water was used to wash the peels, and then distilled water was used to rinse them. The peels were sliced into pieces and allowed to dry in the sun for two weeks. After that, they were blended into a powder using an electric blender, sieved through a 2 mm mesh screen, and kept in an airtight container.

2. 1. 2 Rice (*Oryza sativa*) husk

The rice husk was gathered in May 2022 at the Ehugbo Rice Milling Factory in Afikpo, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The rice husk was sifted to get rid of dirt particles and stones. After being cleaned with water and rinsed with distilled water, the rice husk was left to dry in the sun for two weeks. After being pounded into a powder with an electric blender and sieved through a 2 mm mesh screen, the rice husk was sealed in an airtight container.

2. 1. 3. Yam (*Dioscorea alata*) peel

The New Heavens restaurant in Uturu, Achara Uturu, Abia State, is where the yam peels utilized in this study were gathered in May 2024. Water was used to wash the peels, and then distilled water was used to rinse them. The peels were sliced into pieces and allowed to dry in the sun for two weeks. After being mashed into a powder with an electric blender and sieved through a 2 mm mesh screen, the peels were placed in an airtight container for storage.

2. 1. 4. Yeast used in brewers

The source of the brewer's yeast was Chemicals (Analytical/Research laboratory), located in Uturu, Abia State.

2. 1. 5. Equipment and standard calibration

Spectrophotometer – wavelength band (185 – 1000 nm), Thermometer (0 – 100 °C), Weighing balance, Brix Refractometer, Hydrometer, Penskey-Marten apparatus (ASTM D93A), pH meter.

2. 2. The Fabrication Bioethanol

Acid hydrolysis, fermentation, and distillation are the processes utilized to produce bioethanol.

2. 2. 1. The hydrolysis of acids

Weighed out into a clean, labeled 1000 ml volume flask were 500g of the sieved powdered cassava peels, rice husk, and yam peels, respectively. 500 milliliters of 10% H₂SO₄ were measured, put into each flask with a label, and left for 48 hours. After neutralizing each flask, Whatman filter paper was used to filter the contents into a 1000 ml flask with a label. Each filtrate was used to calculate the amount of sugar in each acid hydrolyzed sample.

At varying intervals of 72 and 96 hours, respectively, the aforementioned experimental methods were carried out again for every sample. Additionally, each sample's acid concentration using 5%, 10%, and 15% H₂SO₄ was changed at a fixed 48-hour interval [21].

2. 2. 2. The Process of Fermentation

Each sample's filtrates were transferred into a 500 ml volumetric flask with a label at a constant temperature of 27 °C. After weighing out 3g of fermentation yeast, it was poured to each flask and left to ferment for 48 hours. The fermented alcohol from each sample was then extracted by distilling each flask. A different time period of 72 and 96 hours was used to repeat the complete fermentation process. The fermentation procedure was repeated using different weights of yeast enzyme (3g, 6g, and 9g, respectively) at a constant time of 48 hours in order to ascertain the impact of enzyme concentrations on the alcohol yield of each sample [22].

2 .2. 3. The fermentation sample is distilled

Using a glass distillation apparatus set at 78 °C, the boiling point of ethanol, the labeled filtrates from each fermented sample were extracted over the course of six hours [23]. From each sample, the distillate was gathered. Therefore, each sample's alcoholic yield was calculated from each distillate.

2. 2. 4. Assess for Ethanol, or Alcohol

The presence of alcohol in each sample distillate was examined using a spectrophotometric device set to 220 nm in wavelength.

2 .2. 5. Measuring the Sugar Content Proportion

The percentage of total sugar in the hydrolyzed cassava, yam, and rice hydrolysate was measured using a refractometer. This was accomplished by putting a drop of their hydrolysate - the filtrate left over after hydrolysis - onto the glass slide of the graduated hand refractometer and calculating the brix value as a percentage. A hand refractometer was used to calculate the brix (%) in accordance with AOAC (2000).

2. 2. 6. Finding the Distillates' Densities

Relative density is shown by the point at which the distillates' surface touches the hydrometer's stem after the distillates were poured into a graduated cylinder and the hydrometer was carefully lowered into the distillates [24].

2. 2. 7. The Distillates' Yield Is Calculated

The yield of bioethanol was computed using the following formula:

$$\text{Yield of bioethanol} = \text{density of bioethanol} \times \text{volume of distillate}$$

2. 2. 8. The pH of the distillates

A pH meter was first calibrated and then placed into each distillate individually. Then, as explained by [25], the readings were obtained.

2. 2. 9. The distilled samples were analyzed using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The infrared light from the Fourier transform infrared instrument was able to pass through each distillate sample thanks to a liquid curvet. The spectrum of each distillate was then recorded as a spectral graph of transmittances versus wave-numbers (cm^{-1}), which displayed different peaks in cm^{-1} that represented distinct functional groups in each distillate [26].

2. 3. Gasoline bioethanol blend

The mixing procedure was used to create a gasoline-bioethanol mixture in the following ratios: 70:30 (E30) to 90:10 (E10). The following report details the ASTM procedures used to test each combination for fuel characteristics:

Table 1. Abbreviation for tested fuel samples.

S/N	Fuel	Abbreviation
1	100% gasoline	Gasoline
2	90% gasoline + 10% bioethanol	E10
3	85% gasoline + 15% bioethanol	E15
4	80% gasoline + 20% bioethanol	E20
5	75% gasoline + 25% bioethanol	E25
6	70% gasoline + 30% bioethanol	E30

2. 4. Assessment of fuel properties

Using the American Standard for Testing Materials (ASTM) protocols for petroleum products, the fuel qualities of the tested blends were ascertained. In order to document the fuel qualities of the evaluated blends, thorough analyses were conducted.

Density, API gravity, viscosity, cloud point, fire point, and heat of combustion were measured for each fuel sample. Using the hydrometer method (ASTM D287 Standard), the density of every tested sample was determined.

The density of each blend was divided by the density of water (0.999 kg/L) to calculate the specific gravity [27, 28].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the bioethanol production and analysis were presented in the tables below.

3. 1. Sugar content of filtrate (%)

Table 2. Percentage Sugar Content of Filtrate at Various Time Intervals at 10% H₂SO₄.

S/N	Sample type	Time (hours)	Volume of filtrate (ml)	Sugar Content (%)
1	RH	48	360	4.3
2	RH	72	360	4.3
3	RH	96	350	4.8
4	YP	48	350	4.5
5	YP	72	340	4.5
6	YP	96	340	4.8
7	CP	48	350	4.5
8	CP	72	350	4.8
9	CP	96	340	4.8

RH – Rice husk, YP – Yam peel, CP – Cassava peel

Table 3. Percentage Sugar Content at Varying Acid Concentrations after Filtration at 48 hours Retention Time.

S/N	Sample type	Acid conc (H ₂ SO ₄) (%)	Volume of filtrate (ml)	Sugar Content (%)
1	RH	5	350	4.3
2	RH	10	360	4.7
3	RH	15	360	4.8
4	YP	5	350	4.8
5	YP	10	340	6.8
6	YP	15	360	6.8
7	CP	5	350	4.8
8	CP	10	350	6.8
9	CP	15	360	7.0

RH – Rice husk, YP – Yam peel, CP – Cassava peel

The percentage of sugar that was formed after the sample was pretreated with acid at varying concentrations of H₂SO₄ was measured using a Brix refractometer. As the quantity of sulfuric acid rose, it was found that the amount of sugar also rose. During the process, the maximum sugar content 7.0% was discovered in 15% H₂SO₄ of cassava peel after 48 hours of retention. Table 3.

3. 2. pH of the distillate

Table 4. pH of the Distillate at Various Time Interval at 3g Yeast.

S/N	Sample type	Time (hours)	Volume of distillate (ml)	pH of distillates
1	RH	48	2	7.25
2	RH	72	2	7.25
3	RH	96	4	7.27
4	YP	48	3	7.28
5	YP	72	3	7.29
6	YP	96	4	7.30
7	CP	48	3	7.30
8	CP	72	4	7.31
9	CP	96	4	7.31

RH – Rice husk, YP – Yam peel, CP – Cassava peel

Table 5. pH of the Distillate at Varying Quantity of Yeast at 48 Hours Retention Time.

S/N	Sample type	Quantity of enzymes (g)	Volume of distillate (ml)	pH of distillates
1	RH	3	2	7.21
2	RH	6	2	7.21
3	RH	9	2	7.28
4	YP	3	4	7.22
5	YP	6	5	7.26

6	YP	9	6	7.30
7	CP	3	6	7.28
8	CP	6	6	7.31
9	CP	9	8	7.33

RH – Rice husk, YP – Yam peel, CP – Cassava peel

The standardized pH meter was inserted into each distillate to determine the pH of the bioethanol. It was shown that, depending on the yeast and time interval, the pH of bioethanol is quite similar. The rationale is that they are all made of the same bioethanol.

3. 3. Density of the distillates

Table 6. Density of Bioethanol at Various Time Interval at 3g Yeast.

S/N	Sample type	Time (hour)	Volume of distillate (ml)	Density of bioethanol (g/ml)
1	RH	48	2	0.7959
2	RH	72	2	0.7960
3	RH	96	4	0.7963
4	YP	48	3	0.7967
5	YP	72	3	0.7967
6	YP	96	4	0.7979
7	CP	48	3	0.7967
8	CP	72	4	0.7979
9	CP	96	4	0.7979

RH – Rice husk, YP – Yam peel, CP – Cassava peel

Table 7. Density of Bioethanol at Varying Quantities of Yeast at 48 Hours Retention Time.

S/N	Sample type	Quantity of enzymes (g)	Volume of distillate (ml)	Density of bioethanol (g/ml)
1	RH	3	2	0.7959
2	RH	6	2	0.7960

3	RH	9	2	0.7963
4	YP	3	4	0.7979
5	YP	6	5	0.7995
6	YP	9	6	0.8063
7	CP	3	6	0.8059
8	CP	6	6	0.8059
9	CP	9	8	0.8075

RH – Rice husk, YP – Yam peel, CP – Cassava peel

The distillates' density was measured using a hydrometer. The fact that each of them produced bioethanol led to the observation that density is about the same. 9g of cassava peel yeast had the highest density in this investigation, measuring 0.8075 g/ml, as indicated in Table 7.

3. 4. Yield of bioethanol

Table 8. Yield of Bioethanol at Various Time Intervals after Distillation at 3g Quantity of Yeast.

S/N	Sample type	Time (hour)	Volume of distillate (ml)	Yield of bioethanol (g)
1	RH	48	2	1.5918
2	RH	72	2	1.5920
3	RH	96	4	3.1852
4	YP	48	3	2.3901
5	YP	72	3	2.3901
6	YP	96	4	3.1916
7	CP	48	3	2.3901
8	CP	72	4	3.1916
9	CP	96	4	3.1916

RH – Rice husk, YP – Yam peel, CP – Cassava peel

Table 9. Yield of Bioethanol at Varying Quantity of Yeast after Distillation .at 48 Hours Retention Time.

S/N	Sample type	Quantity of enzymes (g)	Volume of distillate (ml)	Yield of bioethanol (g)
1	RH	3	2	1.5918
2	RH	6	2	1.5918
3	RH	9	2	1.5926
4	YP	3	4	3.1916
5	YP	6	5	3.9975
6	YP	9	6	4.8378
7	CP	3	6	4.8354
8	CP	6	6	4.8354
9	CP	9	8	6.4600

RH – Rice husk, YP – Yam peel, CP – Cassava peel

By multiplying the volume of the distillates by their density, the yield of bioethanol was determined. The production of bioethanol was found to improve somewhat as the amount of enzyme increased; however, the maximum output, 6.46g, was obtained from 9g of cassava peel yeast, as indicated in Table 9.

The sugar output following acid hydrolysis seems to have substantially matched the bioethanol production from the three agricultural wastes that were examined [29, 30]. This resulted from the yield of 6.46g of bioethanol and 7.0% sugar from cassava peels. Thus, one of the most important conditions for producing bioethanol from agricultural waste is the quantity of sugar that can be converted into alcohol by an enzyme.

3. 5. Verified test for produced bioethanol

A spectrophotometer was utilized to confirm the bioethanol sample from the distillate with the highest yield. The following were the outcomes attained:

The wavelength (nm): 220

The concentration 0.025g/L.

At 220 nm, the absorption spectra were measured [31]. Found that the distillates are bioethanol since the ethanol absorption spectra falls between 210 and 300 nm in wavelength.

3. 6. FTIR results of bioethanol obtained after distillation

The figures below show FTIR results for the highest yield for each of the variations.

Figure 1. FTIR Results for 9g Yeast Pretreated CP.

The O-H group is stretched, as shown by the stretch peak at 3414.2 cm^{-1} in Figure 1. 3056.4 cm^{-1} , 2974.4 cm^{-1} , and 2892.4 cm^{-1} were the C-H stretch peaks, whereas 1714.6 cm^{-1} was the C-O stretch peak.

Figure 2. FTIR Result for 9g Yeast Pretreated YP.

The stretching of the O-H group is represented by the stretch peak at 3488.8 cm^{-1} in Figure 2. The C-H stretch peaks were found at 3056.4 cm^{-1} and 2974.4 cm^{-1} , while the C-O stretch peak was found at 1714.6 cm^{-1} .

Figure 3. FTIR Result for 96hrs Fermentation Period of Pretreated RH

The stretch peaks of the O-H bond were 3459.0 cm⁻¹, the C-H stretch peaks were 3056.4 cm⁻¹ and 2974.4 cm⁻¹, and the C-O stretch peak was 1714.6 cm⁻¹.

Table 10. Functional Groups Obtained from FTIR Analysis of Bioethanol for 96hrs Fermentation Period of Pretreated Rice Husk (RH).

S/N	Peak (cm ⁻¹)	Functional group	Peak type
1	3459.0	O-H	Stretch
2	3056.4	C-H	Stretch
3	2974.4	C-H	Stretch
4	1714.6	C-O	Stretch

The OH stretch of pure ethanol absorbs at a wave number range of 3200 to 3550 cm⁻¹, the C-H stretch absorbs at a wave number range of 2850 to 3300 cm⁻¹, and the C-O bond absorbs at 1050 to 1760 cm⁻¹, according to [32]. The distillates' O-H and C-H stretches fell between 3200 and 3550 cm⁻¹, 2850 and 3300 cm⁻¹, and 1050 and 1760 cm⁻¹, respectively. Thus, it is confirmed that the distillates are pure bioethanol samples. The findings also concur with those of [33], who used rice husk in a related study.

3. 7. Fuel properties of the tested blends

Table 11. Fuel Properties of the Tested Blends.

Fuel blend	Density Kg/L @ 15.6 °C	Specific gravity	API gravity	Kinematic Viscosity mm ² /s @ 30 °C	Flash point °C	Fire point °C	Heat of combustion mJ/L
Gasoline	0.7400	0.7407	59.53	0.4872	-	25.0	34.84
E10	0.7396	0.7403	57.10	0.5383	-	29.0	33.19
E15	0.7495	0.7503	57.09	0.5619	-	29.1	32.91
E20	0.7541	0.7549	55.95	0.6007	29.2	30.0	32.43
E25	0.7571	0.7579	55.21	0.6380	29.6	31.8	31.70
E30	0.7613	0.7621	54.30	0.6614	29.7	31.9	31.53

The blend densities ranged from 0.7400 kg/L for petrol to 0.7613 kg/L for E30, according to Table 11. For E10, it was 0.05% lighter than petrol; but, for E15, E20, E25, and E30, it was

1.26%, 1.87%, 2.25%, and 2.9% heavier than petrol, respectively. It was discovered that when the amount of bioethanol increased, the blends' densities increased steadily. According to these findings, the E30 mix had the highest density of any blend and might be considered a higher-quality fuel, even though all of the blends met the Department of Petroleum Resources' (DPR) standards. It was discovered that the mix API gravities ranged from 54.30 for E30 to 59.53 for petrol. Although the API gravities fell as the bioethanol % rose, they are still within an internal combustion engine's operating range. Since the E30 blend had the lowest API gravity, it might be argued that it is a higher-quality fuel than the others. Blends E10, E15, E20, E25, and E30 were found to have kinematic viscosities that were 10.4%, 15.3%, 23.3%, 30.9%, and 35.7% more viscous than petrol fuel, respectively [34-36].

The flow resistance of a liquid is measured by its viscosity. When using a fuel system to inject or carbureted fuels into combustion chambers, fuel viscosity is a crucial factor to take into account. The fuel will flow too quickly and fail to keep a lubricating layer between the pump's or carburetor's moving and stationary components if the viscosity is too low. An excessively high viscosity may make it impossible to atomize the fuel into tiny enough droplets for efficient burning and vaporization. Despite having the greatest viscosity, the E30 mix was generally within an acceptable range for engines that use spark ignition. Prior to ascertaining its flash point, petrol, E10, and E15 began to burn. Though unrelated to engine performance, the flash point fluctuated with fuel volatility [37-40].

When handling fuel, the flash point is related to safety considerations since the lower the flashpoint temperature, the easier it is to ignite the fuel in the presence of an ignition source. The lowest temperature at which mixes' vapors will burn continuously for at least five seconds after starting is known as the fire point. Although the E10 to E30 blends' fire points fell within the Department of Petroleum Resources' (DPR) allowed range, the E30 blend is thought to have the best flash point and fire point. Blends' respective heat contents dropped by 4.7%, 5.5%, 6.9%, 9.1%, and 9.5% as compared to petrol fuel (34.84 mg/L) for E10, E15, E20, E25, and E30. The decreased heat value of bioethanol was the cause of the blends' declining heating values. These findings showed that the characteristics of petrol bioethanol mixes up to E30 in this study matched the Department of Petroleum Resources' (DPR) criteria, and that, within the parameters employed, the E30 blend is a higher-quality fuel.

4. CONCLUSION

The study's findings could be interpreted as follows: The chosen agricultural wastes yam, cassava, and rice husk peels are thought to make excellent bioethanol production substrates. Utilizing bioethanol derived from yam, cassava, and rice husk peels may greatly lower life cycle greenhouse gas emissions. The amount of bioethanol made from cassava peels was found to be higher than that from yam and rice husks when comparing the agricultural wastes used. A major factor in the generation of bioethanol was the increase in yeast and the amount of time permitted for fermentation. Given the stability of the blending mix, the bioethanol/gasoline blend could be effectively utilized as an alternative fuel for spark ignition engines up to a 30% ratio.

Abbreviations

RH – Rice husk, **YP** – Yam peel, **CP** – Cassava peel, **FTIR** – Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

References

- [1] Agba, A. M. O., Ushie, M. E., Abam, F. I., Michael, S. A., Okoro, J. (2010). Developing the biofuel Industry for Effective Rural Transformation in Nigeria. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 40(3): 441-449
- [2] Chen D, Zheng Z, Fu K, Zeng Z, Wang J, Lu M. (2015). Torrefaction of biomass stalk and its effect on the yield and quality of pyrolysis products. *Fuel* 159: 27-32
- [3] Alriksson, B., Cavka, A., Jonsson, L. (2011). Improving the fermentability of enzymatic hydrolysates of lignocellulose through chemical in-situ detoxification with reducing agents. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 4(2): 89-97
- [4] Aristides, M. O., Salvador, A. R., Junwei, M., Daniel, C., Ernesto, M., Raymond, E. (2014). Applied Spectroscopy. 68(6): 680. DOI: 10.1366/13-07385
- [5] Atsumi, S., Hanai, T., Liao, J. C. (2018). Non-fermentative pathways for synthesis of branched-chain higher alcohols as biofuels. *Journal of Environmental Technology*, 14(7): 86-89
- [6] Barnett, J. A. (2021). The entry of D-ribose into some yeasts of the genus *Pichia*. *Journal of General Microbiology*, 9(1): 1-12
- [7] Behera, S., Singh, R., Arora, R., Sharma, N., Shukla, M. (2015). Scope of algae as third biofuel. *Journal of Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 3: 12-24
- [8] Bender, M. (1999). Economic feasibility review for community-scale farmer cooperatives for biodiesel. *Bioresource Technology*, 70: 81-87
- [9] Beveridge, T. J. (2018). Use of Gram stain in microbiology. *Biotechnology and Histochemistry*, 7(3): 111-118
- [10] Birol, F. and Davie, W. (2011). Oil Supply Costs and Enhanced Productivity. *Energy Prices and Taxes*, 4: 17-22
- [11] Shah MA, Khan MNS, Kumar V. (2018). Biomass residue characterization for their potential application as biofuels. *J Therm Anal Calorim*. 134(3): 2137-2145. doi: 10.1007/s10973-018-7560-9
- [12] Caputi, A., Veda, M. Brown, T. (2017). Spectrophotometric determination of ethanol in wine. *American Journal of Enol. Viticul*, 9: 160-165
- [13] Chen, M., Zhao, J., Xia, L. (2017). Enzymatic hydrolysis of maize straw polysaccharides. *Journal of Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 9: 80-92
- [14] Bolade, D.O.; Ana, G.R.E.E.; Lateef, S.A.; Sokan-Adeaga, A.A. (2019). Exploration of the Bioethanol Yield of Single and Multi-Substrate Biomass from Cassava Processing Wastes. *The Journal of Solid Waste Technology and Management*, 45(3), 305-314(10). <https://doi.org/10.5276/JSWTM/2019.305>
- [15] Da Silva, A., Inoue, H., Endo, T., Yano, S., Bon, P. (2010). Milling pretreatment of sugarcane bagasse and straw for enzymatic hydrolysis and ethanol fermentation. *Journal of Biochemical Engineering*, 5: 31-55

- [16] Demirbas, A. (2008). Biodiesel: A realistic fuel alternative for diesel engine. Springer London, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-84628-995-8>
- [17] Demirbas, A. (2009). Political, economic and environmental impacts of biofuels: A review. *Journal of Applied Energy*, 6: 18-19
- [18] Demirbas, M. F. (2011). Biofuels from algae for sustainable development. *Journal of Applied Energy*, 8: 13-15
- [19] Ibiam Prince Amauche, Udonne Joseph, Jeremiah S. H, and Ezeamama Lilian, (2022). Performance Evaluation and Optimization of a Two Horse Power Concentric Tube Heat Exchanger. *Journal of Engineering Research and Reports* 22(7): 28-38. 10.9734/jerr/2022/v22i717547
- [20] Dmitri, A. B. and Ross, J. R. (2011). Catalysis for conversion of biomass to fuels via pyrolysis and gasification: A review. *Catalysis Today Publication*, 17(1): 1-13
- [21] Mukamal, K., Frish, P., Shink, D. (2016) Alcohol consumption and the risk of coronary heart disease in older adults: the cardiovascular health study. *Journal of American Geriatric Society*, 3(2): 30-37
- [22] Myers, R. L. and Myers, A. E. (2007). The 100 most important chemical compounds: a reference guide. Greenwood Press, London, ISBN-10: 9780313337581
- [23] Nibedita, S., Sumanta, K., Bannerjee, K., Kausta, A. (2012) Bioethanol production from agricultural wastes. *Journal of Renewable Energy*, 4: 19-27
- [24] Nwakaire, J. N., Ezeoha, A., Ugwuishiwu B. O. (2013). Production of cellulosic ethanol from wood sawdust. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering and Extension*, 2: 15-21
- [25] Ortega, N., Busto, M., Perez M. (2011). Kinetics of cellulose saccharification by *Trichoderma reesei* cellulases. *International Journal of Biodeterioration and Biodegradation*, 5(2): 7-14
- [26] Igwebuike, C. M., Awad, S., & Andrès, Y. (2024). Bioethanol production from dilute acid hydrolysis of cassava peels, sugar beet pulp, and green macroalgae (*Ulva lactuca*). *Biofuels*, 15(9), 1145-1157. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17597269.2024.2336328>
- [27] Subhadra, B. and George, G. (2011). Algal biorefinery-based industry: an approach to address fuel and food insecurity for a carbon-smart world. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture, Nigeria*, 9(1): 2-13
- [28] Sun, Y. and Cheng, J. (2019). Hydrolysis of lignocellulosic material for ethanol production: a review. *Bioresource Technology*, 3: 31-38
- [29] Wan, C., Zhou, Y., Li, Y. (2011). Liquid hot water and alkaline pretreatment of soybean straw for improving cellulose digestibility. *Bioresource Technology*, 5: 44-46
- [30] Kaewtrakulchai N, Chanpee S, Manatura K, Eiad-Ua A. (2023). Upgrading of Corn Stalk Residue and Tannery Waste into Sustainable Solid Biofuel via Conventional Hydrothermal Carbonization and Co-Hydrothermal Carbonization. *J Sustain Res.* 5(3): e230012. <https://doi.org/10.20900/jsr20230012>

- [31] Huang, H., Hui, L., Yi-Ru, G. (2010). Genetic modification of critical enzymes and involved genes in butanol biosynthesis from biomass. *Biotechnology Advances Publication*, 2(1): 61-67
- [32] Han, M., Kim, Y., Kim, Y. *et al.* (2011). Bioethanol production from optimized pretreatment of cassava stem. *Korean J. Chem. Eng.* 28, 119-125. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11814-010-0330-4>
- [33] Humphrey, C.N., Okafoagu, U.C, (2007). Optimization of ethanol production from *Garcinia kola* (bitter kola) pulp agro waste. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 6: 33-37
- [34] Hvon, B., Case, J., Faser, D. (2019). Effects of alcohol in humans. *Fraser Journal of Cleaner Production*, 4(2): 30-37
- [35] Ibetto, C. N., Ofuefule, A. U and Agbo, K. E., (2011). A Global Overview of Biomass Potentials for Bioethanol Production: A Renewable Alternative Fuel. *Trends in Applied Sciences Research* 6(5), 410-425
- [36] Feng, P., Xue, S., Yu, S., Zhang, D., Yong, K. (2013). Effects of combination of steam explosion and microwave irradiation pretreatment in enzymatic hydrolysis, sugar yield and structural properties of corn stove. *Journal of Industrial Crop Production*, 6: 23-22
- [37] Sadhukhan J, Martinez-Hernandez E, Amezcua Allieri MA, et al. (2023). Strategic navigation of world-leading biorefineries and Mexico's policy landscape: a gateway to a sustainable circular bioeconomy. *J. Clean. Prod.* 434: 140386. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.140386
- [38] Trivedi N, Gupta V, Reddy CRK, et al. (2015). Enzymatic hydrolysis and production of bioethanol from common macrophytic green alga *ulva fasciata delile*. *Bioresour Technol.* 150: 106-112. doi: 10.1016/j.biortech.2013.09.103
- [39] Singh A, Bishnoi NR. (2012). Optimization of ethanol production from microwave alkali pretreated rice straw using statistical experimental designs by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Ind Crops Prod.* 37(1): 334-341. doi: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2011.12.033
- [40] Nanssou PAK, Jiokap Nono Y, Kapseu C. (2016). Pretreatment of cassava stems and peelings by thermohydrolysis to enhance hydrolysis yield of cellulose in bioethanol production process. *Renew Energy* 97: 252-265. doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2016.05.050